

Writing Revisions of German Learners of English: A Longitudinal Corpus Based Approach

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As part of a PhD project, we will analyse 9000 revisions of students from the truly longitudinal Marburg Corpus of Intermediate Learner English (MILE). It includes handwritten exams from 94 German secondary school students from grades nine to twelve. The data calls for larger quantitatively driven investigations of the sections the students crossed out and how they revised them, as this can tell us about the interlanguage development of the learners. We will focus on two research questions from a longitudinal perspective: In which areas did students revise their writing (content, form, mechanics)? Were their formal revisions successful? We will use a general logistic regression to find the effects of type of revision and revision length on revision success. For that, we will reveal the underlying layers of the final product to be able to see what the final text is hiding:

(1) Mr. Schwarzenegger has a positiv opinion of the USA and *from* California. (0049-2-11-00006)

In 1, we would not have known that the student was struggling with the preposition. Only a process-based approach can reveal the grammatical constructions the students were struggling with or partly aware of, as they improve or worsen their writing through revisions. This poster will briefly discuss how the data was annotated with a taxonomy based on previous ones (Lindgren 2005, Faigley & Witte 1980), while focusing on results from the data annotation of 2000 revisions, accomplished up to this point in the PhD programme. The most important findings were that students were more concerned with content than previously expected and they could revise predominantly successfully. Statistically significant findings showed that spelling revisions were more successfully corrected than revisions concerning abbreviations and multiple word units. The results show promising preliminary findings that could help in the description of the interlanguage of intermediate learners.

References

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